

DETERMINATION OF IMPURITY AND MOISTURE OF RECEIVED COTTON AND CONTROL OF THE QUALITY OF COTTON STORED AT THE PREPARATION POINT.

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Abstract: In this article, to provide more information about the process of raw cotton processing, the effect of using innovative methods, to determine the degree of contamination and moisture of this received cotton, so that they have complete information about this science. The procedure used in the inspection is the law and regulations. Helping them to acquire theoretical knowledge, practical skills and high qualifications from the module "The role and importance of preparation points in the storage of raw cotton and the process of quality control during storage".

Key words: Cotton dirt and moisture interactive method, innovative technology, Preparation point, LKM device, P-2 light polarizing device, desiccator, "Uzdavstandart".

400-500 g from each large jar to small one before analyzing the received cotton for dirt and moisture. a sample is taken from and stored for one day for moisture control. The sample storage time per day is calculated from the time when the controlled part of the sample is placed in a small jar (to

determine moisture) and in a large or jar (to determine contamination). After daily analyzes of moisture and dirt

, the sample residue is left for quality and dirt control and stored in paper bags.

A sample small jar is signed, and a label is attached with the date, farm, brigade, selective and industrial varieties, and groups to be collected. Control after a day samples are added to the appropriate groups.

Innovative technologies are used and samples are selected and analyzed to determine the type, moisture content and contamination of the received cotton in standard samples according to the republican standards numbered 643-95, 592-92, 593-92, 644-95 (1, 2, 3, 4). checked orIt is carried out on instruments certified by the metrological service of "Uzdavstandart". Selection of samples, work of laboratory technicians, laboratory equipment is supervised by the head of TNB of the cotton factory.

The laboratory of the preparation point should have the following devices: Uz-7m cabinet, USX-1 and VXS or VXS-M1 moisture detection device, LKM device for detecting cotton contamination, LPS-4 fiber type detection device, PPV gin fiber cleaner , for cotton SXL-3 laboratory dryer, technical scales with small packing stones, microscope, desiccator with P-2 polarizing device for microscope, jars for taking samples (large and small), LPS-4 instrument, the permissible difference of control checks is not more than 2.5 percent need If the differences between these determinations exceed the permissible amount, then two additional samples are measured in LPS-4 and the average value is calculated according to the measurement results.

The difference between the results of the analysis of two samples should not exceed 0.6% (mut.) in the contamination control analysis when the contamination is up to 10%, and not more than 1.0%

when it is above 10%. Differences between the results of testing two samples in control analyzes should not exceed 0.5% when the moisture content of cotton is up to 10.0% and should not exceed 5.0% (relative) when the moisture content is more than 10%. If the differences between the results of the preliminary and control analyzes do not exceed the above limits, then the preliminary analysis is considered correct.

Daily laboratory analyzes are scheduled to check the correctness of sample selection, to determine the type, contamination and moisture content of cotton accepted by the classifiers and laboratory. For this purpose, on the day after acceptance, combined cotton samples are selected from cotton received on the same day from each batch gathered at the preparation point with the participation of a classifier. Selection and industry of cotton a label indicating the varieties, type of harvest, number of the sampled bunch or batch is attached. After that, according to these samples, the humidity, dirtiness and type of cotton are determined in the laboratory with the help of instruments. The results of the analysis are mandatory for the classifier. According to them, the classifier must take measures to ensure the correct acceptance and collection of cotton. The dirtiness and moisture content of the batch summation data must be in accordance with the acceptance data or may have deviations from the above permissible limits.

In order to assess the quality of the cotton received at the preparation point, the republican standard "Cotton. A middle sample is created according to "Methods of sample selection"

When receiving cotton at the preparation point, it is important to control the quality of the received product. Its accuracy depends not only on the income of the cotton factory, but also on the correct collection of cotton, which ensures reliable storage of cotton. Selection of samples is the first and most responsible process of cotton quality control. Republican standard 643-95 "Cotton. Sample selection methods" (1) are carried out. Sampling is also allowed at cotton unloading sites. For sample selection, a permanent covered porch is usually equipped, and a place is chosen to protect the jars with cotton samples from sunlight, dust and precipitation to determine the moisture and dirtiness of cotton. In order to determine the quality indicators of cotton, a set of samples taken from any point in different places of the brought cotton bunch is made. interactive methods are used.

Bunch is defined as the amount of cotton obtained from one selected industrial variety, which is the same in terms of quality, processed by one transport loader. The classifier of the preparation station selects the samples from each of the indicated bunch points manually until the cotton is weighed with the participation of the cotton supplier. Sampling from points is also allowed in the areas where cotton is unloaded.

A sample of 100-150 g each is selected from at least three places of different depths from every two tons of the brought cotton bunch. The dirtiness and moisture content of cotton is determined in the laboratory of the preparation point within the groups gathered according to the samples for each farm (division or brigade) on an average day.

The average daily sample consists of a collection of cotton samples collected on the same day. It is structured as follows. Cotton samples taken from the points are placed in one small (one kilogram) jar with a tight-fitting lid to be checked for moisture and dirt with the help of instruments.

Its label shows the invoice number, bunch number, types of harvest, and cotton variety of the submitting farm. Then the cotton samples taken from the points collected in small jars are placed in large jars with a capacity of 6-8 kg (the approximate size of a large jar is 0.7 m in height and 0.4 m in diameter). A label is affixed to the big jar indicating the farm, department, brigades, selection and industrial grade of cotton, type of harvest and number of the group to be collected.

Large jars should be stored in a special place in the laboratory or department, away from heating devices. An average daily sample with a capacity of at least 3-4 kg is collected during the entire day of reception, and it is analyzed once a day for moisture and dirt in the laboratory for 3-136. gangs that are grouped by unit, division, brigade, i.e. types of harvest, selection and other signs are carried out accordingly.

CONCLUSION

The methods of the modern approach to determining the moisture and dirtiness of cotton received using the interactive method create an opportunity to arouse interest in conducting scientific research, analyze the state and conditions of the field, learn to introduce new systems, and form theoretical and practical knowledge.

The direct use of "new modern pedagogical technologies" in the teaching process has a good effect. The main problem is the provision of literature, manuals, methodological instructions, handouts, new information and technical tools and the ability to convey them to students.

In this first of all, the teacher himself must have the skills to work with these materials.

To some extent, this problem is solved by the modules prepared by the teacher in this subject. Before studying the theoretical and practical topics of "Drying of raw cotton", students first learn about the importance of the field of drying of raw cotton. In particular, they will have practical skills in improving the technology of growing cotton crops. Based on the above. . How to use this opportunity depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills. In this process, the teacher should be creative and have deep, comprehensive knowledge. In his lessons, he should widely use interactive teaching methods and try to develop students' logical thinking.

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